

Self-realization, Science and the Constitution of India: A Computational Perspective

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Abstract

In this note, the author reflects upon the provisions of the Indian constitution which promote science and related humanities subjects, and their impact upon the individual seeker after self-realization.

At the outset, one must define what is meant by self-realization, without appearing to be presumptuous. However, it is a major aim of many Indians of history and today, notably, Mahatma Mohandas Karamchand Gandhiji. If we go by the literature alone, perhaps the ideal of Sat or Truth and its inculcation, in whichever way one can, seems to be a common thread. The seeker after Sat must confront all that science offers alongside what religion offers. In this relation, of course, the constitution offers clear guidelines in the form of duties numbered e, g, h and j.

These duties encourage a broadening of the spirit of man, an expansion of his or her sympathies and compassion, and if we naturally extend this expansion to its logical extremum, we must embrace the universe ultimately, which is perhaps concomitant with Sat. Thus we can conclude that the constitution, at minimum, does not hinder the seeker after self-realization.

This compatibility between the goal of religions and the constitution of the motherland of many world religions is perhaps not a chance occurrence, but a well-executed part of the vision of the founding fathers, or writers, of the constitution of India.

In this note we examine this triad – science, religion and the constitution – in internally mutual juxtaposition with a view on the integration of science and spirituality which is proposed by the author in [1].

In a series of papers, the author and his co-authors, have developed a view on brain quantum computation, which demonstrates for the first time, quantitatively, the impact of metric perturbations on time-coded information processing in the axon tracts of any nervous system when under conditions of coupling between constituent axons.

The key ingredient which allows this quantification is the extension of traditional neuronal models to three dimensions. This allows the study of waves in the background geometry. These gravitational waves from astrophysical sources, are very weak but nevertheless the Earth is on their path and this has been shown experimentally by the LIGO project and other gravitational observatories.

This model underscores the unity of the brain or nervous system with the cosmos in a hard-to-ignore way. It might be argued that this was already present since neutrinos and other cosmic particles are known to traverse the Earth at all times and therefore also the nervous system. However, their impact on information processing and hence ‘thoughts’ is not well clarified. Metric perturbations, via their geometric foundation, offer this integration with man’s information processing.

This unity is important from a religious standpoint since it shows that thoughts are informed by the most distant events imaginable. This being the case, any argument in favor of a narrow identity of self cannot hold ground. Man is forced from his complacent view of narrowness, out into the open universe in a sense.

This universality of man is enhanced locally when he practices the tenets of constitutional duties [2]. Thus in a way, the constitution encourages the embodiment of universality in the local arena of the nation. In this way, there is a complete harmony between science, the goal of self-realization or Sat and universality, and the tenets of the Indian constitution.

One of the limitations of this view is that these effects are minute, and to boot, they have not been detected yet by our current instruments. A related issue is their falsifiability. The experiments can be conducted, and if at the given sensitivity, the impact is not observed that can be said to be a falsification of one of two things – the integration of general relativity with computational neuroscience, or, general relativity and / or computational neuroscience individually. The integrated view stands on a foundation of theory and simulations at this juncture.

That said, it is clear that the constitutional duties still would stand, whether or not the new theory is upheld, and so their logical end must still be viable of attainment.

References

1. Chawla, Aman and Morgera, Salvatore Domenic. Computer Study of Metric Perturbations Impinging on Coupled Axon Tracts. Physics Essays. 2024.
2. Agrawal, P. K. and Gupta, V. The Constitution of India: Bare Act With Short Notes. Prabhat Exams.